

Quanti Farm

BENCHMARKING TOOL

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FACTSHEET #5

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WHAT IS IT?

The **Benchmarking Tool** is an interactive component of the **QuantiFarm Toolkit** that supports the **comparison of agricultural performance across parcels, time periods, and farming practices**.

It enables users to **cross-reference farm management events, meteorological measurements, and calculated indicators** to analyse differences between **different parcels or the same parcel over time**.

By combining user-provided parcel data with recorded cultivation practices and environmental measurements, the tool generates **performance indicators** that allow users to benchmark resource use and management outcomes under real farming conditions.

WHO IS IT FOR?

The Benchmarking Tool is designed for:

Farmers & Farm Managers

seeking to compare performance between parcels or seasons

Advisers and advisory services

supporting evidence-based farm management decisions

Researchers and Analysts

analysing cultivation practices and performance indicators

Technology and Innovation stakeholders

interested in understanding DATS-related impacts at the parcel level

The tool supports users who wish to explore **data-driven comparisons** of agricultural practices and outcomes.

KEY OBJECTIVES

To enable benchmarking of farm performance indicators across parcels and time periods

To support the comparison of management practices, including irrigation, fertilisation, spraying, and harvesting

To link cultivation practices with environmental and meteorological data

To support evidence-based evaluation of Digital Agriculture Technology Solutions (DATSs)

To enhance understanding of resource use and management efficiency under different farming conditions

MAIN FEATURES

Parcel-level data management

Users can create and manage parcels individually or through CSV import, including spatial boundaries.

Farm calendar event recording

Supports structured recording of key operations such as sprays, irrigations, fertilisations, and harvests.

Meteorological data integration

Enables the inclusion of measurements such as temperature, humidity, wind, rainfall, and leaf wetness.

Indicator calculation and benchmarking

Automatically generates aggregated indicators (e.g., totals, averages, minimums, maximums) and specialised calculations (e.g., chilling days).

Cross-parcel and temporal comparison

Allows direct comparison between different parcels or different periods of the same parcel.

Links to DATSs' resources and Test Cases

Results can be connected to relevant DATSs information and QuantiFarm Test Cases, providing contextual insights.

Together, these features support systematic benchmarking and comparative analysis of agricultural performance at parcel-level.

Learn
More

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